

Linx (pseudonym) : Automated Calculation of Hyper-parameters for Data Linking and its Impact on Linking Accuracy

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<https://www.overleaf.com/project/645a27bdacda251f7a8a164>

Abstract. Data linking is a crucial process to connect different data sources and make them usable together. Traditional approaches use experts' manual intervention to design linking rules. Even recently, neural-network-based approaches have used handcraft-based hyper-parameters selection for the linking tasks. In this paper, we promote an automated data linking approach that computes hyper-parameters efficiently and accurately, eliminating the need for costly and time-consuming manual intervention. These hyper-parameters are computed by aggregating the similarity matrices obtained at the predicate and object levels associated with the training datasets. We use matrices in mathematical formulas to numerically represent the most relevant features of the data. Then, we estimate similarity hyper-parameters that optimize the data linking accuracy. We validated our approach on several datasets (14) and obtained promising results in terms of accuracy and sometimes in computation time. We developed a previous approach, Linx, that uses a configuration of hyper-parameters. Our system participated in OAEI 20xx and was ranked first and second in two challenges. Our new approach is fully automatic in the hyper-parameters computation but also flexible because the users can modify them afterward.

1 Introduction

Data linking is a key technique in many applications of life, from computer vision to data matching in databases. This technique involves finding a correspondence between instances of two different datasets, which allows for the discovery of correspondences and associations between data. However, data linking can be challenging [1], as data sets can be of different sizes and structures [4, 5, 13], and instances can be difficult to compare directly.

Over the years, many methods for data linking have been proposed. Traditional approaches initially proposed manually defined alignment rules [5, 7, 31, 32]. More recent approaches, such as geometry-based and machine learning-based approaches, proposed semi-automatic alignment methods. Machine learning-based approaches have seen rapid growth recently due to the advancements in deep learning and neural networks, which enable a more accurate comparison of instance features.

However, to our knowledge, there is no fully automatic method for defining the optimal hyper-parameters to use for effectively training neural networks. We first developed Link, using manual hyper-parameters and participated in the 202x competition of Ontology Alignment Evaluation Initiative (OAEI). Our system was ranked first and second in two challenges respectively. This work has as a goal to fully automate the procedure of data linking automatically creating the hyper-parameters and proceeding to the linking step.

This article presents an approach for automatic hyper-parameter calculation based on extracting matrices (predicate and literal levels) of similar instances from training data. The Linx tool uses these hyper-parameters, once they are calculated, to perform data linking tasks. We demonstrate that our method is competitive with existing methods on several benchmark datasets and can be extended to more complex problems such as key discovery [35] and link prediction [38]. In the rest of this article, we explain our motivations in Section 2, review existing approaches and their general techniques in Section 3, formalize our approach for automatic hyper-parameter calculation from training data in Section 4, evaluate this formalized approach in Section 5, and conclude in Section 6.

2 Motivations

Automated data linking is a crucial task for many applications. The data linking tasks requiring manual configuration can be very tedious and time-consuming, especially if datasets are large. With an automated linking solution, the process is accelerated and can be performed more efficiently. Our main motivation was the fact that the first version of Linx still required manual assistance to perform the linking process. Thus, we wanted to improve the automatic and optimal search for the hyper-parameters that are required for the linking task of Linx.

3 Related work

Data linking problem can be classified into several categories based on their methods and purpose. Among them we can cite feature matching-based approaches [2, 3, 9–11, 15–18], structure-based approaches [5, 13], deep learning-based approaches [12, 19, 20], and graph-based approaches [5–8].

Feature matching approaches involve extracting features [24, 25] from the instances in each dataset and then finding pairs of matching instances using similarity measures. On the other hand, structure-based approaches exploit the intrinsic structure of datasets to find matches between instances. Deep learning-based [21, 22] approaches are widely used in recent years and consist in

learning representations of the instances that allow a more accurate comparison and better matching between datasets. Graph-based approaches use the graph structure to link instances in a global way [23]. In the graph-based methods, some methods use graph structure to link instances, such as the random graph linking method [38, 39].

In the literature LIMES [7] uses a vector space metric-based approach, where data is transformed into vectors and alignments are found by calculating distances between these vectors. In addition, We have LogMap [32] that enables ontology alignment by detecting correspondences between concepts and appropriately associating them. LogMap exploits logic-based reasoning and diagnosis techniques to ensure similarities between concepts and optimally align them. Users can also customize alignment strategies according to their specific needs. Building on the previous statement, we were inspired by the work of LIMES to produce matrix representations of the training dataset. Like LIMES' vector representations, our matrix representations will be used by mathematical formulas to calculate the hyper-parameters. By generating these matrix representations, we aim to improve the efficiency and accuracy of our manual model by using a more robust, automatic, and structured approach to the data. Finally, it is important to note that automatic instance linking approaches are still under development, and new approaches and techniques are constantly emerging.

4 Method and Material

4.1 Description of the approach

Our approach is primarily based on using data in the RDF format, which allows storing data as triples (subject, predicate, object). We have two inputs to match: a data source (source) and a data target (target), as well as an output (outputs). For the training dataset, a ground truth associates similar entities using the owl:sameAs predicate. Three hyper-parameters (HP1, HP2, HP3) are used in our approach. HP1 is the threshold value used for comparing literals, while HP2 represents the number of predicate pairs whose object comparison exceeds the threshold. Lastly, HP3 determines the depth of similarity search between literals during comparison. Our automated data linking process uses training on ground truth data that already contains established owl:sameAs links. It consists of several steps. First, matrices associated with each pair of ground truth instances are generated at the predicate and object level. Next, We mathematically calculate the local hyper-parameters for each pair of similar instances using the matrices. Then, we aggregate these different hyper-parameters to produce the final set of hyper-parameters for the training dataset. Finally, we use these hyper-parameters to link existing data in another process using Linx.

Fig. 1. Overview of our approach. (1) involves preparing the training data or ground truths. (2) involves leveraging the training data to generate matrices and compute hyper-parameters. (3) Linx use the datasets and hyper-parameters calculated from the ground truths on the real data.

4.2 Formalization

Preliminaries. Consider an RDF data source (a graph) as a set of triples defined by : $G = \{(s, p, o) \in (R \cup B) \times (R) \times (L)\}$, where R is the set of all resources in the form of IRIs, B is the set of blank nodes and L is the set of literals. We denote the set of RDF data sources by D . Let $S(G)$, $P(G)$, $O(G)$ be the respective sets of subjects, predicates and objects of a given dataset G , respectively. Let \mathbb{N} be the set of natural numbers including 0. Let us consider $i, j, k, m, n, d, d_{max}, k_{max} \in \mathbb{N}$ which can be dependent or independent on the expression of the function they define as well as the context of application. We also consider the set $Same_{As} = \{(s, owl : sameAs, s')_k; 0 \leq k \leq k_{max}, s \in S(G_1), s' \in S(G_2) \text{ with } G_1 \text{ and } G_2 \in D\}$. $Same_{As}$ is the set of training data sets containing the ground truths ($Same_{As} \subset D$ and $owl : sameAs$ is the linking predicate of the instances). The value of d_{max} is automatically computed and represents the number of common sub-sequences between two literals. Henceforth, the notation $(s, s')^k$ is used equivalently to $(s, owl : sameAs, s')_k$.

Definition of functions and symbols. To make our approach easier to understand, we have created a symbol and function table that lists all the symbols and functions used in our mathematical formulas. Table 1 shows each symbol associated with a meaning and each function described with its arguments and output.

Functions	Symbols	Descriptions
-	(i, j)	Placed under a matrix, it allows to realize a projection on it. eg : (i, j) for the j-th column and $(i, -)$ for the i-th row.
$\lceil v \rceil$	-	returns the integer close to $v (v \in \mathbb{R})$. eg : $\lceil v = 0.75 \rceil = 1$
$\lfloor v \rfloor$	-	returns the decimal part of v by subtracting its integer part. eg : $\lfloor v = 4.56 \rfloor = 0.56$
$ S $	-	provides the number of elements that constitute S . eg : $ \{s1, s2, s3, s4, s5\} = 5$
\bar{E}	-	calculates the average value of the numeric elements of E .
$\min(v1, v2)$ or $\min(vector)$	-	returns the minimum numerical value between $v1$ and $v2$ or the smallest value of the <i>vector</i> of array type.
$\max(v1, v2)$ or $\max(vector)$	-	returns the maximum numerical value between $v1$ and $v2$ or the highest value of the <i>vector</i> of array type.
$argmax_d(vector)$	-	returns the index d of the highest value of the <i>vector</i> of array type.
$\phi(M)$	-	The value that appears most frequently in M , $[\phi(M)]$ returns the frequency of the mode eg: $M = [[1, 2], [3, 1]]$, $\phi(M) = 1$, $[\phi(M)] = 2$.
$f^a(A)$	-	f is a projection(query) function on the sets that returns the set of a directly associated or contained in A . eg : $f^p(s)$ return the set of p (predicates) directly associated with s (subject). eg : $f^s(same_{As})$ return the set of s (source subjects) contained in $same_{As}$ (set of training data).
$lcs^d(l_1, l_2)$	-	This function returns the d -th longest common subsequence (lcs) between two literals, whose size is smaller than the previous subsequence.
$sim^d(l_1, l_2)$	-	returns the average similarity between the two literals at depth d . $\frac{ lcs^d(l_1, l_2) }{\min(l_1 , l_2)}$

Table 1. Functions and Symbols with usage examples for improved understanding in our approach.

Generation of the matrices. To clarify the representation of matrices for predicates and objects for $(s, s')^k$, we provide an example in Figure 2. In this example, we consider the pair (ldb:person1, rdb:person1) as similar based on ground truth or training data, and align the predicates associated with literals (excluding resources). We generate the respective similarity matrices containing the similarity values of the LCS calculated at the predicate and object levels, spread over different depths. The title of the figure might help you to understand the intuition in the figure

Fig. 2. Example of the generation of matrices on training datasets. In this example, in (1), we have 4 predicates pairs because there are 2 predicates which have the literals as value in each instance. In (2) and (3), we have the values computed for each row using the process shown in (4). In (4), each average similarity is associated with the depth d and the length of the LCS is 32($d=0$) because its prefix is associated with a URI value. (4) stops when it no longer finds a common sub-sequence between the literals.

Consider the following function, which takes two instances and the generation axis of the matrix then returns the associated matrix. $M_{n,d_{max}}([0,1])$ is the set of matrices of order (n, d_{max}) with values in $[0,1]$. We can distinguish whether the matrix M is a similarity matrix resulting from the comparison at the level of predicates or objects of the pair of instances by examining the value of the exponent "a". For $(s, s')^k$ that match, we generate a matrix of average similarity values of correspondences spread over the lower depths d_{max} at the predicate and object levels.

$$M^a : \begin{array}{l} S(G_1) \times S(G_2) \longrightarrow M_{n,d_{max}}([0,1]) \\ s \times s' \longrightarrow \begin{bmatrix} \alpha_0^0 & \dots & \alpha_0^{d_{max}-1} \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \end{bmatrix} \end{array}$$

Let us now define the specific cases of our matrices in mathematical terms at the level of predicates ('a' as p) and objects ('a' as o). To ensure a smooth execution of the algorithm, we made the wise decision to harmonize the dimensions of the matrices by inserting zeros so that all rows have the same size. This strategy optimized the algorithm performance by avoiding any risk of blocking. It will also help to eliminate some rows or columns during the operations by reducing the aggregate value (e.g. the average).

- $M^p(s, s') = \{\alpha_i^d = sim^d(p, p'); \forall (p, p')_i \in f^p(s) \times f^{p'}(s'); 0 \leq i < n = m = |f^p(s)| \times |f^{p'}(s')|, 0 \leq d < d_{max}\}$:
i-th row of the matrix represents the average similarities at comparison *d-th* depth of the predicate pairs (p, p') of $(s, s')^k$;
- $M^o(s, s') = \{\alpha_i^d = sim^d(o, o'); \forall (o, o')_i \in f^o(p) \times f^{o'}(p'), \forall (p, p') \in f^p(s) \times f^{p'}(s'); 0 \leq i < n \times m; n = |f^o(p)| \times |f^{o'}(p')|, 0 \leq d < d_{max}\}$:
i-th row of the matrix represents the average similarities at comparison *d-th* depth of the pairs of objects (o, o') belonging, respectively, to the pairs of predicates (p, p') of $(s, s')^k$. *m* is the number of predicate pairs associated with $M^p(s, s')$.

Operations on matrices for $(s, s')^k$ and Computation of Hyper-parameters.

- To find the best unique predicate pairs, we compute the $M^p(s, s')$ matrix. First, for $(s, s')^k$, we simply select the predicate pairs whose more than half of the values in the associated average similarity vector are greater than 0. Then, a selection of unique predicate pairs is made on the union of all intermediate selections;
- $\tilde{O} = max(max(\bigcup_{i \in \{0, \dots, n-1\}} \overline{M_{(i, -)}^o}(s, s')), max(\bigcup_{j \in \{0, \dots, d_{max}-1\}} \overline{M_{(, j)}^o}(s, s')))$:
 Here we look for the row or column that has the largest average value and consider its value as the threshold at the object level during the comparison;
- $\tilde{d} = argmax_d(\bigcup_{d \in \{0, \dots, d_{max}-1\}} \overline{M_{(, d)}^o}(s, s'))$:
 Here we are looking for the depth of the column that has the maximum average value;
- $\tilde{A} = min([\phi(\bigcup_{i \in \{0, \dots, n-1\}} M_{(i, -)}^o(s, s')), [\phi(\bigcup_{j \in \{0, \dots, d_{max}-1\}} M_{(, j)}^o(s, s'))])$:
 Here we are looking for the smallest frequency of the most frequent value in the matrix based on the union of the rows and columns axis.

After computing the hyper-parameters at the instance pair level, we proceed to estimate their global averages for use by Linx.

Same _{As}	threshold of comparison on objects(HP1)	acceptance threshold(HP2)	threshold of comparison depth(HP3)
$\{(s, s')^k\}$	$\lfloor \text{sum}(\bigcup_{k \in \{0, \dots, k_{max}\}} \tilde{O}_k) \rfloor$	$\lceil \overline{(\bigcup_{k \in \{0, \dots, k_{max}\}} \tilde{A}_k)} \rceil$	$\lceil \overline{(\bigcup_{k \in \{0, \dots, k_{max}\}} \tilde{d}_k)} \rceil$

Table 2. Hyper-parameters considered during the training phase. k_{max} represents the number of $(s, s')^k$.

- HP1 : This value is determined by adding up the intermediate hyper-parameters (\tilde{O}) for $(s, s')^k$ and then extracting the decimal portion;
- HP2 and HP3 : These values represent the average of the intermediate hyper-parameters for (\tilde{A}) and (\tilde{d}) associated with $(s, s')^k$, respectively.

5 Experimental Results

5.1 Environment

We tested our new approach for automatic data linking on the last OAEI 20xx⁵ campaign and achieved good results in 9 challenges. We evaluated our tool on different datasets and compared the results with other tools such as LogMap [32], Oto [28], Lance [30], Radon [34], Silk⁶, DS-JedAI, AML [33], RIMOM [31] and Eagle [29]. We selected these tools as they analyzed the same datasets as us. Rather than re-executing the other tools, we preferred to focus on the benefits of our approach in terms of traceability in the data linking process. We did not find any tools that perform automatic data linking, and we noted that all of the above mentioned tools require manual configuration. The experiments for the automatic version of Link were conducted on an 11th Gen Intel(R) Core(TM) i9-11950H @ 2.60GHz with 32GB of main memory running Ubuntu 20.04.4 LTS on kernel Linux 5.14.0-1059-oem with x86-64 architecture. However, the manual version of Link was executed on a Linux virtual machine with 256 GB of RAM and 32 vCPUs (2.4 GHz).

⁵ https://hobbit-project.github.io/OAEI_20xx.html

⁶ <https://github.com/silk-framework/silk/issues/57>

5.2 Datasets

To conduct our experiments, we used the SPIMBENCH [26] and UOBM [27] datasets available in the OAEI dataset collection⁷. SPIMBENCH describes its datasets using a rich ontology with many different OWL constructions, while UOBM uses a simpler ontology with many object properties and some data type properties. We evaluated the 2016 (small and large) and 2019 (small) datasets from SPIMBENCH, and only the small-sized dataset from UOBM. The number of triples processed for the small-sized datasets is approximately 10K for both datasets, and 51K for the large-sized dataset.

TOMTOM and SPATEN are sent from SPATIAL benchmark generator⁸ that store topological relationships in the form of SPATIAL resources that can be linked together. These SPATIAL resources are described from a large information set such as LinkedGeoData. This Benchmark supports several topological relations (Equals, Disjoint, Touches, Contains/Within, Covers/CoveredBy, Intersects, Crosses, Overlaps). This SPATIAL generator contains three data generators (TomTom, Spaten and DEBS).

5.3 Results and Discussions

- In the Table 4, we avoided unnecessary comparisons between predicate objects by automatically identifying key predicates from source and target that actively contribute to instance matching. The unique selection of predicate pairs is done by retaining only those whose at least half of the values of the associated average similarity vector in the predicate matrices are greater than 0. In this way, we selected 6 predicate pairs from 540 potential pairs on the US16 dataset. In addition, we found that 4 active predicate pairs out of 112 potential pairs were selected for the three Spimbench datasets (SS16, SL16, SS19). We also note that aligned predicates share semantically correct common points, this simplifies the search for hyper-parameters in the Table 3;
- Our evaluation in the table 5 on UOBM small 2016 shows that we achieve an f-measure of 0.849, compared to Oto (0.75), Logmap (0.6, 0.32), RIMOM (0.821), AML (0.665) reference [36]. The evaluations also conducted on Spimbench small (2016 and 2019) produce an f-measure of 0.899 for both, compared to RIMOM (0.992), Logmap (0.851), AML (0.82) reference [37]. Linx was less effective than Logmap during the OAEI 20xx campaign with an f-measure of 0.702 compared to 0.841 in the sandbox. Finally, we conducted our evaluations on Doremus as well but with two scenarios (automatic and manual from the automatic value). In automatic, we achieve an f-measure of 0.756, precision of 0.608, and recall of 1.0, while in the manual configuration of hyper-parameters obtained by readjusting the automatic values, we obtain an f-measure of 0.857, precision of 0.75, and recall of 1.0, which is between RIMOM (0.813) and AML (0.918) [37]. Eagle and Lance have never evaluated UOBM dataset [36]. Please note that even if ss16 and ss19 provide the metrics, they are not the same dataset because the hyper-parameters are different;
- In the figure 3 and 4 below, we have the results of Linx’s participation in the OAEI 20xx for link discovery with hyper-parameters manually searched on open datasets provided by OAEI have been added. Linx maintained the first place in its 8

⁷ <https://users.ics.forth.gr/~jsaveta/.index.php>

⁸ <https://github.com/hobbit-project/SpatialBenchmark>

challenges in terms of high precision in a short time on both sandbox and mainbox. Linx did not appear to be effective on large spimbench datasets.

Datasets / hyper-parameters	threshold of comparison on objects(HP1)	acceptance threshold(HP2)	threshold of comparison depth(HP3)
UOBM small 2016 (US16)	0.668	1	0
Spimbench small 2016 (SS16)	0.664	1	0
Spimbench Large 2016 (SL16)	0.202	1	0
Spimbench small 2019 (SS19)	0.744	1	0
Doremus(auto)	0.283	2	0
Doremus(auto reajusted manually)	0.700	2	0

Table 3. Computed hyper-parameters on each Dataset. We adjusted the HP1 hyperparameter automatically generated for the doremus dataset to investigate its impact on the accuracy of our results and the flexibility of our approach.

SandBox Linestrings - Linestrings : EQUALS - OVERLAPS

Fig. 3. Results of Linx on SandBox for TOMTOM and SPATEN.

MainBox Linestrings - Linestrings : EQUALS - OVERLAPS

Fig. 4. Results of Linx on MainBox for TOMTOM and SPATEN.

Datasets	US16	SS16, SL16, SS19	Doremus
Pred. pairs	540	112	35
Selected pairs	6	4	4
Pred. used	<pre>prefix pf:<http://semantics. crl.ibm.com/univ-bench-dl.owl#> pf:lastName-pf:firstName pf:firstName-pf:firstName pf:emailAddress-pf:lastName pf:emailAddress-pf:firstName pf:lastName-pf:lastName pf:firstName-pf:lastName</pre>	<pre>prefix pf:<http://www.bbc.co.uk/ ontologies/creativework/> pf:description-pf:description pf:shortTitle-pf:shortTitle pf:title-pf:dateModified pf:title-pf:title</pre>	<pre>prefix p1:<http://data. doremus.org/ontology#> prefix p2:<http://erlangen-crm. org/current/> p1:U12_has_genre-p2:P3_has_note (p1:P3_has_note- p2:U16_has_catalogue_statement) p1:P3_has_note-p2:P102_has_title p1:P102_has_title-p2:P102_has_title</pre>

Table 4. Key predicate pairs : This table lists the pairs of predicates that were automatically selected, after eliminating a large number of pairs that could have slowed down the data linking process on each dataset.

Tools/Datasets	US16			SS16			SS19			SL16			Doremus(auto—manual)		
	P	R	F	P	R	F	P	R	F	P	R	F	P	R	F
Linx	0.737	1.0	0.849	0.818	1.0	0.899	0.818	1.0	0.899	0.470	1.0	0.640	0.608—0.75	1.0	0.75—0.85

Table 5. This table presents the results obtained from running Linx with the hyper-parameters associated with Table 3 on the data from different datasets.

6 Conclusion and Future Work

Automatic linking of RDF instances is a crucial task for data integration. Our approach which automated hyper-parameters computation has shown promising results. In our previous work, we developed Linx, a semi-automatic data linking tool that required the design of four hyper-parameters for its proper functioning. We worked on an approach for automatic generation of these hyper-parameters and found that only three of them are necessary (excluding the threshold hyper-parameter for predicate comparison). We evaluated our approach on popular benchmarks and compared the results with other data linking tools. We obtained good results since the approach infers hyper-parameters automatically. Thus, we can observe that processing similarity matrices using mathematical formulas provide an effective and accurate way to link data instances. Moreover, this approach has also demonstrated its ability to retrieve key predicates that greatly contribute to the process of key predicate detection, which is essential for data linking. Additionally, Linx leaves the possibility to control manually these hyper-parameters. Indeed, the system tests several hyper-parameters configuration and rank them by their best accuracy but at the end, the user can modify them regardless of whether these hyper-parameters have been generated. Automatic data linking between instances is a promising direction for future research in the field of data integration and semantic web applications. It is important to remember the differences between manual and automatic data linking approaches, with the latter offering advantages such as efficiency, scalability, and cost-effectiveness. Our approach has shown that it is possible to improve the performance of automatic link establishment. In the future, we plan to integrate the management of synonyms sentences during the comparison of literals to enrich the features to be extracted between instances.

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Supplemental Material Statement: The source code is attached to the article submission. Start by reading the file ‘_Alert_README.txt’ to run the reproducibility procedure in 4 steps.

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